

Terrain-Driven Vertical Alignment Optimisation : with Evolutionary and Swarm-Intelligent Methods

Aditya Veera Venkata Reddy Sathi

Abstract. Vertical alignment design for highways is a complex, nonlinear optimisation problem due to terrain irregularities, earthwork interactions, and strict engineering grade limits. To address this, this study investigates the use of natural computing techniques for optimising road elevation profiles over real SRTM terrain. A horizontal corridor is first generated using A*, after which the path is sampled into stations and evaluated through a unified constraint-aware fitness function capturing cut–fill earthwork, haulage, structural penalties, and grade violations. Hill Climbing, Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO), a Genetic Algorithm (GA), and a hybrid GA–PSO method are implemented and tested across multiple terrain maps to assess performance and robustness. Results show that the GA–PSO and PSO consistently achieves the lowest cost and smoothest, demonstrating the effectiveness of nature-inspired optimisation for continuous engineering design tasks with strong physical constraints.

1 Introduction

Road alignment optimisation has traditionally been separated into horizontal and vertical design tasks. Early approaches applied deterministic curve-fitting using tangents or parabolic segments, which performed well on smooth terrain but failed under irregular elevation data and nonlinear cost structures. As methods evolved, researchers reformulated alignment design as an optimisation problem. Although fully integrated 3D models have been proposed (e.g., [4]), most studies still focused on either dimension independently. For vertical alignment in particular, metaheuristic approaches such as PSO and ACO have been widely explored [6, 7]. In this work, similar vertical-optimisation perspective has been followed.

Many studies first generate a baseline horizontal corridor using discrete path-search methods such as grid-based DP, Dijkstra-type algorithms, distance transforms, or RRT variants [5, 3]. A vertical optimisation stage is then applied on top of this fixed corridor, typically using GA, PSO, ACO, DE, or hybrid natural-computing methods.

Cost modelling is also central to alignment design, with earthwork-cut, fill and haulage-typically dominating total cost. Constraint-aware fitness functions are widely used to enforce grade limits and smoothness requirements so a similar cost function to [2] was used.

Following these developments, this study adopts a two-stage framework: A* is used to generate a feasible horizontal corridor on real SRTM terrain, after which hill climbing, PSO, GA and a GA–PSO hybrid are applied to optimise the vertical alignment. A unified cost function enables a controlled comparison of these natural-computing methods.

2 Background

Highway alignment is a challenging optimisation problem because construction cost, terrain geometry, and engineering constraints interact in highly nonlinear ways. Early deterministic and curve-fitting methods were effective only on smooth terrain and simple cost models, but they performed poorly once real elevation data and heterogeneous land-use layers were introduced. Chan and Fan [8] demonstrated this by integrating GIS with a Genetic Algorithm (GA), showing that cut–fill costs, right-of-way penalties, and terrain discontinuities create a search space unsuitable for gradient-based optimisation. Their work established natural-computing methods as a viable alternative for alignment design.

Other studies strengthened this direction. Shafahi and Bagherian [6] showed that Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) is well-suited to continuous design variables such as grades and elevation profiles, and that raster-based GIS significantly accelerates earthwork evaluation. Their results confirmed that metaheuristics can outperform conventional engineering alignments, particularly in rugged terrain.

Broader evolutionary-optimisation research also contributes relevant ideas. demonstrated that diversity-preserving selection improves convergence in multimodal landscapes [1]

Overall, the literature points to a clear trend: natural-computing and hybrid metaheuristics provide the flexibility and robustness needed for terrain-driven alignment problems, motivating the use of hill climbing, PSO, GA, and a GA–PSO hybrid in this study.

3 Experiments and results

3.1 Terrain Data and Preprocessing

A sandbox test area was defined by a central latitude–longitude point and radius. SRTM elevation and OSM water features were rasterised onto a uniform grid, forming the base surface. Light denoising (median filtering, artefact removal, Gaussian smoothing) was applied to reduce SRTM noise while preserving terrain shape. The cleaned terrain–water grid served as the input for all optimisation experiments.

3.2 Experimental Setup

A* search was applied on this raster to generate a feasible horizontal corridor that avoids steep slopes and water penalties. The path was uniformly sampled into stations, which define the vertical-alignment optimisation domain.

All optimisation algorithms—HC, PSO, GA, and GA–PSO—were evaluated using the same engineering cost function. Fixed end elevations enforce boundary consistency. A unified metric set was

used for comparing the algorithms: final cost, improvement (percentage gain over baseline), runtime (computational efficiency), mean $|Z - \text{ground}|$ (average elevation deviation), grade-penalty frequency (number of points incurring a grade penalty), average penalty magnitude (mean excess over the allowable grade), and smoothness metrics (TVC and TAOVVC measuring curvature and vertical-curve variability).

$$\begin{aligned}
J(z) = & C_{\text{cut}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \max(-(z_i - g_i), 0) \Delta s_i w \\
& + C_{\text{fill}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \max(z_i - g_i, 0) \Delta s_i w \\
& + C_{\text{haul}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |z_i - g_i| \Delta s_i w \\
& + \lambda (s_N - s_1) \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \left[\max\left(\left| \frac{z_{i+1} - z_i}{\Delta s_i} \right| - G_{\text{max}}, 0\right) \right]^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Equation 1 defines the objective function used for evaluating the algorithms. The first three terms represent cut, fill, and haulage volumes; and the final term imposes a quadratic penalty for slopes exceeding the allowable gradient G_{max} . Each algorithm in this study tries to minimize $J(z)$ under fixed boundary constraints.

3.3 Model Architecture and Training

Four optimisation methods were tested: Hill Climbing (HC), Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO), a Genetic Algorithm (GA), and a GA–PSO hybrid. Each searches for the elevation vector z that minimises the cost function $J(z)$ (Eq. 1) under fixed end-point constraints. Across all methods, z_i denotes the design elevation at station i , g_i the ground elevation, and Δs_i the station spacing.

Hill Climbing (HC). HC performs stochastic local search. At each step a single index i is perturbed by Gaussian noise,

$$z'_i = z_i + \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2),$$

and the update is accepted only if $J(z') < J(z)$. Restarts reduce the chance of remaining in local minima.

Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO). PSO maintains a swarm of candidate profiles. Particle p updates its velocity v_t^p and position z_t^p using

$$v_{t+1}^p = \omega v_t^p + c_1 r_1 (p_t^p - z_t^p) + c_2 r_2 (g_t - z_t^p), \quad z_{t+1}^p = z_t^p + v_{t+1}^p,$$

where ω controls inertia, c_1 and c_2 weight the attraction to the particle's personal best p_t^p and the global best g_t , and r_1, r_2 are random coefficients. Velocities and elevations are clipped to enforce the bounds.

Genetic Algorithm (GA). The GA evolves a population of profiles. Each generation applies: (i) tournament selection; (ii) BLX- α crossover, which samples each gene from an extended interval between two parents; (iii) Gaussian mutation; and (iv) elitism to retain the best individuals. This maintains diversity while reducing the overall cost.

Hybrid GA–PSO. The hybrid first runs GA for global exploration. The best GA output added with some noise initialize the PSO swarm, after which the PSO performs local refinement. This two-stage design takes advantage of GA's broad search and PSO's strong convergence.

Problem Encoding. All algorithms operate on the same real-valued representation. A candidate solution is encoded as an elevation vector

$$\mathbf{z} = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N) \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

where z_i denotes the design elevation at station i . In GA this vector is treated as a chromosome; in PSO it forms each particle's position (with an associated velocity vector of equal dimension).

3.4 Algorithmic Configuration and advanced features

Table 1. Key optimisation parameters used in the experiments.

Algorithm	Parameter	Value
Genetic Algorithm (GA)	Population size	40
	Generations	500
	Crossover rate	0.90
	Mutation rate	0.10
	Mutation std. (σ)	0.5
Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO)	Particles	40
	Iterations	500
	Inertia weight (w)	0.7
	Acceleration terms (c_1, c_2)	1.5, 1.5
GA–PSO Hybrid	GA stage	100
	PSO iterations	400

Table 1 summarises the optimisation parameters adopted for all runs.

Hybridisation methods used in this study include a GA–PSO two-stage scheme (GA seeding PSO with its best and perturbed solutions) and an optional GA→HC refinement, supported by stability features such as domain-aware initialisation, elevation clipping, velocity limits, and BLX- α crossover with Gaussian mutation.

3.5 Result

Figure 1. Vertical profiles and convergence behaviour for all optimisation algorithms and hybrids.

Figure 1 shows that the PSO clearly outperform the standalone algorithms. Hill Climbing diverges from the terrain and converges slowly due to its purely local search behaviour. GA achieve smoother curve but plateau early, indicating premature stagnation. In contrast, GA–HC refinement hasn't done any improvement, and the GA–PSO hybrid achieves the second lowest cost and smoothest elevation trace after PSO. The log-scale convergence curves further confirm this pattern: only the hybrid GA–PSO, PSO methods continues

Table 2. Cost-oriented performance metrics for each optimisation algorithm.

Algorithm	Final Cost	Improve (%)	Mean $ Z - G $
HC	9.16×10^6	83.98	0.7961
PSO	4.84×10^4	99.92	0.8887
GA	4.99×10^5	99.13	0.9426
GA-H	4.99×10^5	99.13	0.9426
GA+PSO-H	6.41×10^4	99.89	0.9308

Table 3. Constraint and smoothness metrics for each optimisation algorithm.

Alg.	Gmax Ex. (%)	A-Gmax (%)	TVC	TAOVVC
HC	41.38	4.39	1.7319	1.2179
PSO	6.90	9.36	0.7589	0.3358
GA	6.90	10.31	0.9990	0.2453
GA-H	6.90	10.31	0.9990	0.2453
GA+PSO-H	3.45	10.19	0.8304	0.1275

improved throughout the run, demonstrating stronger global-local balance and more effective optimisation on noisy real terrain.

Tables 2 and 3 show that PSO achieves the lowest final construction cost, slightly outperforming GA-PSO. However, PSO's advantage comes with weaker constraint handling: its Gmax exceeds and smoothness metrics (TVC, TAOVVC) are noticeably worse than those of the hybrid method. The GA-PSO hybrid offers the best overall balance, achieving strong cost reduction (second best after PSO) while delivering the lowest Gmax exceedance, lowest TAOVVC, and improved smoothness. These gains result from GA-initialised PSO populations, which prevent premature stagnation and produce cleaner, more feasible elevation profiles than pure PSO.

4 Discussion

The experimental results highlight clear behavioural differences between all algorithms.

The results show that Hill Climbing performs the worst due to its greedy nature.

PSO and GA both achieved strong cost reductions, though their behaviours differed. PSO reduced cost rapidly, reflecting its tendency to move the swarm toward consistently improving regions of the search space. GA progressed more gradually but maintained more regular profiles and haven't improved much after some point.

The hybrid GA-PSO method benefited from using the GA output as a structured starting point for PSO. As the results clearly show that GA-PSO has better metrics score in Gmax and TAOVVC compared to base PSO

The results show that each algorithm exhibits different strengths: PSO achieves the lowest cost but performs poorly on grade compliance and smoothness. The GA-PSO hybrid does not lead every metric, but it provides the most balanced trade-off overall, offering strong cost reduction while significantly improving constraint handling compared with standalone PSO.

5 Conclusion and future work

The results show that tightening the grade limit from 6% lower rate it changes the relative performance of the algorithms. At Gmax = 0.06, the GA-PSO hybrid performs best on most metrics, whereas at Gmax = 0.05 or lower the standalone PSO achieves the lowest cost and lower violation rates. This shift indicates that both methods respond differently to stricter grade constraints: PSO benefits

from its strong exploitation behaviour but remains less smooth overall, while the hybrid maintains more regular profiles but does not always achieve the lowest violations or cost under the tighter bound. Overall, neither method is uniformly superior, each has strengths and weaknesses that become more or less pronounced depending on the chosen grade limit.

The discretizations experiment further showed that finer station spacing increases the likelihood of grade violations for all methods, but the hybrid remains the most robust, sustaining significantly lower exceedance rates across resolutions.

Future work should extend the framework toward multi-objective optimisation (eg. [4]), explicitly balancing cost, smoothness, and environmental impact. Incorporating right-of-way constraints, material-balance models, and bridge/tunnel geometry would allow more realistic design scenarios. Finally, adapting modern machine-learning surrogates or reinforcement-learning search policies could substantially reduce runtime while retaining optimisation performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Noe Casas. Genetic algorithms for multimodal optimization: a review, 2015.
- [2] T. F. Fwa, W. T. Chan, and Y. P. Sim, 'Optimal vertical alignment analysis for highway design', *Journal of Transportation Engineering*, **128**(5), 395-402, (Sep 2002).
- [3] Hans Heinimann, Jürg Stükelberger, and Woodam Chung, *Austro2003: High Tech Forest Operations for Mountainous Terrain*, 2003.
- [4] Jyh-Cherng Jong and Paul Schonfeld, 'An evolutionary model for simultaneously optimizing three-dimensional highway alignments', *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, **37**(2), 107-128, (2003).
- [5] Neville A. Parker, 'Rural highway route corridor selection', *Transportation Planning and Technology*, **3**(4), 247-256, (1977).
- [6] Yousef Shafahi and Mehdi Bagherian, 'A customized particle swarm method to solve highway alignment optimization problem', *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, **28**(1), 52-67, (2013).
- [7] M.B. Sushma, Sandeepan Roy, and Avijit Maji, 'Exploring and exploiting ant colony optimization algorithm for vertical highway alignment development', *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, **37**(12), 1582-1601, (2022).
- [8] Chan Weng Tat and Fan Tao, 'Using gis and genetic algorithm in highway alignment optimization', in *Proceedings of the 2003 IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, volume 2, pp. 1563-1567 vol.2, (2003).